

ISic1333

I.Sicily inscription 1333

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2015.10.22

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8748

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140829

1. [— — —]#⁷T [— —]
2. [— — —]AΘI [— —]
3. [— —].IOY#⁷ [— —]
4. [— —]AIEIM [— —]
5. [— —]ICΛ [— — —]
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492941

EDCS 39101706

PHI 140829

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0512 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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